

Potential and Average Force in Quantum Mechanics

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Quantum mechanics makes use of a potential $V(x)$ (or $V(x,t)$) which we argued in a previous note (1), may be written as $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V(k) \exp(ikx)$ on what should be physical grounds. Thus, $-d/dx V(x)$ is only an average force, which may in fact be zero, while the pieces $-d/dx V(k) \exp(ikx)$, which act at different times, give rise to forces and motion/acceleration to the left and right. The constraint is that the average force over time be zero. In this note, we argue that the $\exp(ikx)$ portion of force may itself be stochastic (with different probabilities at different x values) in addition to any given $V(k) \exp(ikx)$, which yields a momentum hit of k .

In this note, we consider the example of a particle in a box with an infinite potential at both ends. The wavefunction is proportional to $\sin(px)$ with $p=2(3.14) n/L$ where L is the length of the box. It has been argued (2), that the Fourier transform of a step function brings in all momentum terms, thus for $\sin(px)$, p is an average momentum. Other momenta are stirred up because of the step function wall. We argue in this note, that other momenta may be stirred up if there is a constant potential because one may write: $V \text{ constant} = \text{Sum over } k \ V(k) \exp(ikx)$. If this is true, a quantum free particle moving in a region with a potential, but no force, may also feel effects from $V(k) \exp(ikx)$. We argue this may be related to the Ehrenberg–Siday–Aharonov–Bohm effect. If one changes the value of the constant potential for the particle in a box, kinetic energy behaviour does not change, but total energy does. E in $\exp(iEt)$ (the time portion of the wavefunction) represents physical cycling even though it disappears from the spatial density expression. We argue this increased cycling is due to larger momentum hits from $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ (due to probability changes) because V_k changes. Thus, even though the spatial part of the wavefunction and average kinetic energy at each point remain unchanged, $\exp(iEt)$ and physical behaviour change.

Stochastic $V(x)$

In (1), we argued that $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V(k) \exp(ikx)$ on what should be physical grounds. Thus, $V(x)$ and $-d/dx V(x)$ are averages. At any given time, a $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ may act, thus there is stochastic behaviour related to which momentum hit k will occur at a time. Each $V(k) \exp(ikx)$, however, is stochastic because if $-d/dx V(k) \exp(ikx)$ yields a momentum hit of k in a region Δx then:

Force(k) = $dp/dx \ dx/dt$ where $dp = k$ and $dx = \Delta x$. There is no reason for dx/dt to be of the form $V(k) \exp(ikx)$, it is the velocity of the particle, unless $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ is linked to a probability. At x , for example, there is a momentum distribution given by:

$P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ where $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} \ ((1))$

Thus, there is a probability associated with having a certain velocity related to $\exp(ipx)$ and this seems to be linked to $V(k) \exp(ikx)$.

If one considers k and $-k$ (at different times) with $V(k)=V(-k)$, then:

$$V(k) = 2 \cos(kx) \quad ((2))$$

The potential (and corresponding k force) are periodic in x and may yield a positive or negative hit of k , causing a particle to move or accelerate to the right or left. The probability for the force which transfers k momentum may increase or decrease with x leading to similar motion in the probability of having a particular p at x i.e. $P(p/x) + P(-p/x) = 2 a(p) \cos(px)$ if $a(p)=a(-p)$.

What is unusual is that the term $V(k) \cos(kx)$ (associated with $k/-k$) is related to the force $-k V(k) \sin(kx)$ which is positive for some x and negative for others and is larger for some x points and smaller at others. Thus, the work done by this force may be larger in some places and smaller in others and the change in the average kinetic energy due to $F(k)+F(-k)$ larger and smaller in different places, yet each momentum distribution entry $a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ receives the same momentum hit of k and $-k$ at different times. This seems to lead to the probability $P(p/x)+P(-p/x)$ being periodic in x as well and ultimately affects the spatial density. If $V(x)$ is an average over time, may one consider $F(k,x)+F(-k,x)$ to also be an average? For example at x_1 , $\sin(k x_1)$ may be a large number (relative to 0) meaning there is a high probability of a k being delivered while at x_2 , $\sin(k x_2)$ is much smaller suggesting a lower probability of k being delivered. In other words, at a given time, one must first choose a $V(k) \exp(ikx)$, but then depending on the position x there is a further probability that it will deliver a momentum of k and a probability that it will deliver nothing. If a particular $F(k)+F(-k)$ has very little probability of delivering k or $-k$ momentum at x , another $F(k_1)+F(-k_1)$ may have a high probability of delivering $k_1/-k_1$ at this same point at a different time. If probabilities are involved, one would expect a normalization constant i.e.

$\sin(k x_1)$ is proportional to the probability of a $k/-k$ being delivered and $1 - \sin(k x_1)$ to the probability of no momentum being delivered i.e. no work being done. The normalization constant is then: $\sin(k x_1) + 1 - \sin(k x_1) = 1$.

Quantum mechanics seems to deal with time averages, but the different partial forces switch on and off or reverse sign in a periodic fashion over x . This may explain why the spatial density is written as a sum of terms of the form: $a(p_1) \exp(i p_1 x) + a(p_2) \exp(i p_2 x)$. There is a probability to have $a(p_1) \exp(i p_1 x)$ at x , but there is also a probability $a(p_2) \exp(i p_2 x)$ that p_1 will change to p_2 . The x dependence is related to the $\exp(ikx)$ which is part of every $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ term. Just as the strange $\sin(k_1 x)$ behaviour allows for the $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ terms to ultimately create $V(x)$ on average, the same behaviour allows for the $a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$'s to create average kinetic energy at x . In the case of momenta, there are many values and so there must be a normalization constant $W(x)$ which is 1 for the $V(k) \sin(kx)$ case.

Coupling of $V(x)$ and the Wavefunction

We argue the average potential and average force are really due to a force that is stochastic on two grounds. First, there is a sum of $F(k)$ (where $F(k)$ yields a hit of momentum k) as each $F(k)$ may act at a different time. Secondly, given a particular $F(k)$ or $F(k)+F(-k)$ with $V(k)=V(-k)$ i.e. $2 V(k) k \cos(kx)$, one may have a probability which changes with x for $k/-k$ to be delivered. (The alternative is no $k/-k$ is delivered.) A momentum distribution is created at x given by $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$, yet if one has average kinetic energy at x plus $V(x)$ equal to a constant energy then:

$$\text{Sum over } p \ p^2/2m \ a(p) \exp(ipx) + V(x)W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((3))$$

Thus, there may be a coupling of $V(x)$ with $W(x)$. In other words, an $\exp(ikx)$ from $V(x)$ may couple with an $\exp(ip_1 x)$ from $a(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x)$ to create an $\exp(i(k+p_1) x)$. Thus, given any $\exp(ipx)$ from the momentum distribution, it may be created by various other p_i values of a particle coupling with different k values from $V(x)$. If one considers ((3)) for a single $\exp(ipx)$ then:

$$a(p) \ p^2/2m + \text{Sum over } k \ V(k) a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, the second term on the LHS represents a coupling or cycling related to the total energy E . We argue that $\exp(iEt)$ represents physical cycling. Changing $V(k)$ changes E and cycling as well. Let us attempt to apply these ideas to a particle in a box with infinite walls.

Particle in a Box with Infinite Walls

Traditionally in quantum mechanics, the problem of a particle in a box with infinite walls is solved by obtaining a solution to the Schrodinger equation which vanishes at the endpoints i.e. $W(0)=W(L)=0$ i.e. $W(x)=A \sin(px)$. This has the form of a sum of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ and is often thought of as a wave moving forward and another backwards. If one obtains the Fourier transform of a step function (at the wall), however, all $\exp(ikx)$ terms enter, thus $\exp(ipx)$ in the solution represents an average p according to (2). Thus, there are many other momenta k stirred up. Is there physical evidence for this? It seems there may be if one considers tunneling through a wall potential which is less than infinite to be based on a particle actually receiving a large momentum above the average barrier level.

Consider now the scenario of a constant potential within the box. According to $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k \ V(k) \exp(ikx)$, one may break a constant potential into a sum of $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ pieces which should in turn create a momentum ensemble. It may be noted that $V(k) = B \int dx \exp(-ikx) V(x)$ and so incorporates global information about the potential throughout x . The point we make is that having a potential in space may be enough to stir up a momentum distribution, even though the wavefunction $\text{Sum over } k \ a(k) \ exp(ikx)$ may look like $\exp(ip_{ave} x)$ or $\sin(p_{ave} x)$. For a particle in a box with infinite walls, this is the case, but it may also be the case for a particle travelling through a region with a constant potential and no force. Thus, a region with no

force may still affect a quantum particle. There may be some forward and backward motion (causing a delay compared with another potential value). This seems to be somewhat reminiscent of the Ehrenberg–Siday–Aharonov–Bohm effect. In fact, in (3) a calculation is performed using perturbation theory for a region with a potential which yields no average force. The energy is changed slightly in this region, so $\exp(iEt)$ changes and the authors show this change may be written in terms of path integral through space.

Consider the case of a constant potential in more detail. The potential does not affect the wavefunction in the box. $\sin(px)$ where $p=2(3.14)n/L$ is still a solution and the average kinetic energy at each x remains the same, but the potential is V_c and the energy are both greater than for the $V_c=0$ case. If E is greater, this affects $\exp(-iEt)$ which represents physical cycling. $\exp(-iEt)$ disappears from spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ and is sometimes ignored, but we argue it should be linked to physical behaviour. Thus, systems with V_{c1} and V_{c2} should physically differ. We note that: $V_k = \text{Integral (endpoints)} + V_{ci} \text{ Integral } dx \sin(kx)$, so changing V_c changes V_k . This in turn changes the work done by $V(k) \exp(ikx)$. Thus, even though $W(x)$ does not change overall, there seem to be microscopic changes. If V_{c1} increases, V_k increases and work increases suggesting more back and forward kinetic energy i.e. faster microscopic speeds (although the average speed remains unchanged). This might account for faster cycling times represented by $\exp(-iEt)$.

What happens if V_c is kept constant, but L increases? In this case, one has the extra term: $\text{Integral } L_{\text{original}} \text{ to } L_{\text{new}} dx \sin(kx) V_c$. The result oscillates with L_{new} values, so there is no systematic change as in the $V_{c1} \rightarrow V_{c2}$ situation. In addition, E does not change in this new case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we wish to stress two points. First, we argue $V_k \exp(ikx)$ is associated with a force which yields a momentum hit of k , but $V_k \exp(ikx)$ is periodic in x and may represent an average in time with different probabilities at each x . For example, at x_1 $V_k \exp(ikx)$ delivers k with a probability of $V_k \exp(ikx)$ and 0 with a probability of $1 - V_k \exp(ikx)$. Thus, there are two stochastic features. First, $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and one must choose a k at t_1 , but even so, one must next consider x because it determines the probability for this V_k to actually deliver k (momentum) instead of 0 momentum.

Secondly, we argue that even for a constant potential with no average force, one may use $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$. Thus, there may be forward-backward hits to the particle even in such a case and these may be related to the physical cycling implied by $\exp(iEt)$. If one increases V_c , then E and the cycling frequency increase. V_k increases and so the work done by each $V_k \exp(ikx)$ increases implying higher microscopic kinetic energies and thus perhaps a higher frequency. Different V_c values give rise to different disturbances (back and forth) and so one may expect different phases for a particle moving through a region with V_{c1} and V_{c2} , as in the Ehrenberg–Siday–Aharonov–Bohm effect.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Effect of a "Stochastic" Potential in Bound State Quantum Mechanics Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2020)
2. Majernik, Vladimir; Richterek, Lukas (1997-12-01). "[Entropic uncertainty relations for the infinite well](#)". J. Phys. A. 30 (4): L49. [Bibcode:1997JPhA...30L..49M](#). [doi:10.1088/0305-4470/30/4/002](#). Retrieved 11 February 2016.
3. Saldana, P. Local Description of the Aharonov-Bohm effect with a quantum electromagnetic field (2020)